

Data Management Plan structure and objectives

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ai4realnet.eu

DMP – An overview

Guidelines on FAIR Data Management in Horizon 2020, European Commission, 2016

- Key for good data management
- Blueprint for what will be done with the data
- Living working document

Source: <https://www.openaire.eu/how-to-make-your-data-fair>

DMP – An overview

Guidelines on FAIR Data Management in Horizon 2020, European Commission, 2016

- Data must be described, along with documentation
- Deposited in suitable repositories
- Assigned a digital object identifier (DOI) for a stable and consistent way to find the data

Benefits

- Research integrity
- Credit for researchers
- Saves time and resources

What is FAIR DATA?

DMP manager

- Development and updates of the DMP
- Support data publication
- Point of contact for DMP related questions

about

Supported the development of 13 DMPs since 2022

DMP - Developing the first version

Approach

- Mapping good practices and align them with the structural DMP components
- From core practices to more specific ones
- Top down – with researchers' input

DMP components

- Data summary
- FAIR data
 - Repository selection
 - Data documentation
 - File naming convention
- Data security
- Allocation of Resources
- Ethics and Legal Compliance

Data Summary

- An assessment of how the data will be collected, including existing data or third-party sources that will be used.
- A brief description of the datasets (mostly high-level technical and administrative metadata)

Format: .xml Mode of data collection: literature review and interviews Data collection instrument: no specific (text analysis)	DOI: 10.5281/zenodo.7708751 Availability: Open (embargoed until paper issued, available upon request)
Data Type: data from surveys Date created: 2023-jul Number of data files: 1 Format: .xml Mode of data collection: online survey Data collection instrument: SPSS/R	Personal data: yes Sensitive data: no Update frequency: not foreseen Storage location: institutional drive Availability: private

FAIR Data

- When, where, which and how the data will be made available
- What documentation and metadata has accompany the data

Repository selection

Institutional

Catch-all

Disciplinary

Data specific

Data Security

- Prevention against the risk of data loss – what's the backup strategy?
- The definition of access conditions – who has access to the data?

Ethical and Legal Compliance

- Roles and Responsibilities in the management of personal data – DPO.
- Definition of consent forms, adoption of data minimisation principle and anonymization.

What do I need from you?

Answer a form that aims to gather information about the different DMPs components (by partner)

- What is the aim of the data generation and its relation to the overall objectives of AI4REALNET?
- Can you specify when and under which conditions the datasets can be made available?
- How the data will be documented to ease its reuse?
- What data storage and backup strategies are in place to keep the data safe?

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